

REDEMOS

RECONFIGURING EU DEMOCRACY
SUPPORT. TOWARDS A SUSTAINED
DEMOS IN THE EU'S EASTERN
NEIGHBOURHOOD

Gender Mainstreaming Plan

Table of Contents

GLOSSARY OF TERMS	3
Sex	3
Gender	3
Gender equality	3
Intersectionality	3
Equal opportunity for women and men.....	4
Gender-sensitive research	4
1. Introduction: defining gender mainstreaming.....	5
2. Gender equality as a legal obligation and normative commitment in the EU.....	5
3. Gender mainstreaming in research.....	7
3.1 The composition of research teams.....	7
3.2 Integrating gender into research content (gender-sensitive research)	8
3.3. Gender-sensitive communication, dissemination and impact.....	10
3.4 Implementation, monitoring and evaluation.....	11
REFERENCES	14

GLOSSARY OF TERMS

Sex

According to the European Commission's Toolkit Gender in EU-funded research, sex "refers to the biologically determined characteristics of men and women in terms of reproductive organs and functions based on chromosomal complement and physiology. As such, sex is globally understood as the classification of living things as male or female."

Gender

According to the [World Health Organisation](#), gender "refers to the characteristics of women, men, girls and boys that are socially constructed. This includes norms, behaviours and roles associated with being a woman, man, girl or boy, as well as relationships with each other. As a social construct, gender varies from society to society and can change over time. Gender is hierarchical and produces inequalities that intersect with other social and economic inequalities. [...] Gender interacts with but is different from sex, which refers to the different biological and physiological characteristics of females, males and intersex persons, such as chromosomes, hormones and reproductive organs. Gender and sex are related to but different from gender identity [which refers to] a person's deeply felt, internal and individual experience of gender, which may or may not correspond to the person's physiology or designated sex at birth."

Gender equality

Being a Sustainable Development Goal (SDG5), a fundamental right and key principle of the European Pillar of Social Rights, gender equality – according to the [UN Women Training Center glossary on definitions](#) "refers to the equal rights, responsibilities and opportunities of women, men, girls and boys. Equality does not imply sameness but that the rights of women and men will not depend on the gender they were born with. Gender equality implies that the interests, needs and priorities of all genders are taken into consideration, recognising the diversity of different groups. Gender equality is not a women's issue but should concern and fully engage all genders while recognising that neither all men nor all women are a homogenous group." Put differently, gender equality implies that no individual should be discriminated against or treated differently based on their gender and that men and women should have the same access to education, healthcare, employment and other areas of life.

Intersectionality

The [European Institute for Gender Equality](#) defines 'intersectionality' as an "analytical tool for studying, understanding and responding to the ways in which sex and gender intersect with other personal characteristics/identities, and how these intersections contribute to unique experiences of discrimination." The objective of adopting an intersectional perspective in research, policy and practice is, on one hand, to acknowledge that "gender is closely linked to other sources of inequality and exclusion", and, on the other hand, to ensure that the resulting multi-layered and intersecting situations of "discrimination, vulnerability and marginalisation" are recognised and the structures and power dynamics that underpin them are questioned, as suggested by the [Handbook on Gender Mainstreaming for Gender Equality Results](#).

Equal opportunity for women and men

According to the [European Commission's Toolkit Gender in EU-funded research](#), "equal opportunity indicates the absence of barriers to economic, political and social participation on the grounds of sex. Such barriers are often indirect, difficult to discern and caused by structural phenomena and social representations that have proved particularly resistant to change. Equal opportunities, which is founded on the rationale that a whole range of actions are necessary to redress deep-seated sex and gender-based inequities, should be distinguished from equal treatment, which merely implies avoiding direct discrimination."

Gender-sensitive research

In gender-sensitive research, gender is consistently taken into account throughout the research cycle. Put differently, and according to the EU-funded [GARCIA project](#), gender-sensitive research "takes into account the differences between men and women in all aspects of the research, from an initial idea, formulating research questions, objectives and methodologies to the outcomes and presentation of results. Apart from integrating gender into the content, gender-sensitive approach strives to provide equal participation of both women and men in scientific work. Gender-sensitive approach takes into account transgender and transsexual population as well."

1. Introduction: defining gender mainstreaming

At the **United Nations Fourth World Conference on Women in Beijing** in September 1995 **gender mainstreaming** was endorsed as the global strategy for achieving **gender equality** and strengthening **women's rights and empowerment**. While there is no 'one size fits all' formula for gender mainstreaming that can be applied across different contexts, sectors and issues, what unites mainstreaming approaches is a commitment to making gender equality a ubiquitous concern in public life, rather than merely an 'add on' (United Nations, 2002, 2).

The **ECOSOC agreed conclusions (1997/2)** thus define gender mainstreaming as:

'...the process of assessing the implications for women and men of any planned action, including legislation, policies or programmes, in all areas and at all levels. It is a strategy for making women's as well as men's concerns and experiences an integral dimension of the design, implementation, monitoring and evaluation of policies and programmes in all political, economic and societal spheres so that women and men benefit equally and inequality is not perpetuated. The ultimate goal is to achieve gender equality.'

Similarly, the **Council of Europe (1998)** definition of gender mainstreaming emphasises:

*'The (re)organisation, improvement, development and evaluation of policy processes, so that a gender equality perspective is incorporated in all policies at all levels and at all stages, by the actors normally involved in policy-making.'*¹

2. Gender equality as a legal obligation and normative commitment in the EU

As a fundamental value, gender equality is a key component of the international human rights law regime, stipulated, inter alia, in the **Universal Declaration of Human Rights**, the **International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights** and the **Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women** (United Nations, 1948; United Nations, 1976; United Nations, 1979). The **2030 Sustainable Development Agenda** has reaffirmed - through its Sustainable Development Goal 5 - the critical importance of gender equality and the empowerment of all women and girls. In addition, it has integrated gender equality as a cross-cutting priority through all SDGs, thus confirming the transformational potential of gender mainstreaming.

Within the EU, gender equality has long represented a concern in the context of policy development, going back to the **EEC Treaty signed in Rome in 1957**. Since that time, the European Union has adopted 13 directives in the field of gender equality, including on equal pay and social security, protection of pregnant women and people on parental leave, and access to goods and services. More recently, the Council, in its **Conclusions on Women, Peace and Security** of 10 December 2018, stated that 'Gender equality and Human Rights are at the core of European values and constitute stand-alone priorities mainstreamed across all EU policies', while the **EU Strategic Approach to Women, Peace and Security** which followed from these, set out to provide, concretely and holistically, "a solid basis for realising

¹ <https://www.coe.int/en/web/genderequality/what-is-gender-mainstreaming>

equality between women and men [...] by engaging, empowering, protecting, and supporting women and girls to achieve peace and security.” These commitments built on, amongst others, the **New European Consensus on Development** of 2017 and the **European Parliament’s** report on ‘**Gender Equality in the EU’s foreign and security policy**’ of 23 October 2020. Both make it unmistakably clear that gender equality and awareness of gender are guiding principles in all areas of EU policy-making, both internal and external. Internally, the **EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025** “aims at achieving a gender equal Europe”, while externally the **EU’s Gender Action Plans (I, II and III)** strive to “promote gender equality and women’s empowerment through all external action of the European Union.” An example of such an effort to support gender equality externally that is relevant to the region researched by REDEMOS is the three-year programme "**EU 4 Gender Equality: Together Against Gender Stereotypes and Gender-Based Violence**" launched by the EU in 2020 together with UN Women and UNFPA and which seeks to tackle gender stereotypes and gender-based violence in the six countries of the Eastern Partnership: Armenia, Azerbaijan, Belarus, Georgia, Moldova, and Ukraine.

The EU’s approach to gender equality is embedded in a wider framework whereby, according to Article 10 of the **Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union (TFEU)**, when “defining and implementing its policies and activities, the Union shall aim to combat discrimination based on sex, racial or ethnic origin, religion or belief, disability, age or sexual orientation”. This approach, drawing on intersectionality as a cross-cutting principle, continues to be the cornerstone of the EU’s efforts towards gender mainstreaming, as stated in the EU Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025.

Gender equality in science and research emerged as a key priority in need of a more formal and expansive approach in the wake of the Amsterdam Treaty (1999) which established equality between men and women as a specific task of the Community and as a horizontal objective affecting all Community tasks. The European Commission (EC) subsequently issued the Communication **Women and Science: mobilising women to enrich European research**, thus formalising its commitment to advancing gender equality in research (European Commission 2009).

Under **Horizon 2020** gender became for the first time a cross-cutting issue, aiming to produce more gender-sensitive content in research and innovation, an objective which resulted in several ‘gender-flagged’ topics across the programme (European Commission, 2009). **Horizon Europe** has gone even further in requiring by default the integration of the gender dimension into research and innovation content.² Within the European Union’s Horizon framework, there are several important documents that provide guidelines for promoting gender equality in research and innovation: Horizon Europe Framework Programme, Horizon Europe Gender Equality Plan, Horizon Europe Work Programmes, Guidelines on Gender Equality in Horizon Europe. These documents aim to ensure that gender considerations are integrated into Horizon projects and contribute to creating a more inclusive and equitable research landscape.

² https://research-and-innovation.ec.europa.eu/strategy/strategy-2020-2024/democracy-and-rights/gender-equality-research-and-innovation_en

3. Gender mainstreaming in research

Gender mainstreaming as a strategy aiming at achieving gender equality must be adapted to the particular issue, sector or activity it aims to target, given the diversity of opportunities and limitations present in every area of work. In addition, each issue-area raises specific concerns that warrant particular analytic approaches to be adopted and questions to be asked. When it comes to research, three specific elements emerge as particularly relevant for a Gender Mainstreaming Plan:

3.1 The composition of research teams

Gender mainstreaming research projects in terms of the structure of research teams typically concerns two aspects:

A) Equal opportunities for women and men in research and empowering women to participate in research and science

Working within mixed research teams has been shown to be more efficient and creative than single-sex teams (European Commission 2009). The potential for academic excellence and breakthrough science is enhanced when collaborative projects attract the widest possible pool of talent. At the same time, it is undeniable that the academic 'leaky pipeline' systematically leads to women disappearing from senior and leadership positions where they are still woefully underrepresented. These two important considerations inform the REDEMOS approach to the configuration of its research teams, and the composition of its governing bodies more generally. On one hand, the Consortium' female-male researcher ratio is exactly 50/50, while the research teams of every single work package are led by a female researcher and the Project Coordinator (PC), leading also the Project Management Team, is a female academic. Guided by the ambition to counter underrepresentation of female researchers in leadership positions in academia and generate an empowering dynamic, the REDEMOS governing bodies – both of a decision-making (Steering Group) and advisory (Ethics Committee; Gender Board; International Advisory Board) nature – are predominantly led and represented by women, without excluding the participation of men. These types of 'targeted interventions' in support of narrowing the gender gaps that disadvantage women are in no way contradictory to a gender mainstreaming strategy, but rather complement efforts geared towards gender equality (United Nations, 2002).

In addition, all partners pursue an equal opportunity policy at their respective institutions and many are actively engaged with innovative initiatives aimed at fostering gender in R&I (e.g. NTNU's 'gender balance from below' initiative; TUD's 'Gendered University' project; YSU's Center for Gender and Leadership Studies, offering innovative solutions to promoting gender equality).

- **RECOMMENDATION:** REDEMOS partners should continue to strive towards gender balanced research teams as they recruit new team members, and make sure to avoid gender bias and discrimination in selection and recruitment procedures, working conditions and culture and management practices.
- **SUPPORT MEASURE(S):** REDEMOS will offer training on gender sensitivity in recruitment and management practices.

B) Gender expertise of researchers

When it comes to conducting gender-sensitive research, an important aspect is the inclusion of researchers with relevant expertise and experience on gender and the integration of gender perspectives in research. Within the REDEMOS consortium, several individual researchers carry out research on specific gender topics (e.g. Dr Laura Chappell; CRRC), publishing in renowned outlets revolving around gender (Dr Theofanis Exadaktylos) or demonstrate through their published (open source) research how their scholarly work is sensitive towards gender and gender inequality matters (e.g. Dr Eka Metreveli; Dr Kristi Raik). This is complemented by partners' regularly held public activities on issues related to gender (e.g. IDIS; GFSIS; YSU).

- **RECOMMENDATION:** REDEMOS should ensure that the perspectives of researchers with gender expertise are appropriately considered and widely shared across work packages.
- **SUPPORT MEASURE(S):**
 - Researchers with gender expertise will be invited to occasionally give talks to consortium members on the gender dimension(s) of REDEMOS research, as well as to provide advice on how gender perspectives can be incorporated into project research.
 - Relevant resources (presentations; guidelines; webinars) will be made available to project partners in the relevant shared Teams channels.

3.2 Integrating gender into research content (gender-sensitive research)

Under Horizon Europe, by comparison to previous EU research and innovation framework programmes such as Horizon 2020 and FP7, **integrating the gender dimension into research and innovation content** represents an operational objective and has become a mandatory requirement (Horizon Europe Programme Guide 2023). This is achieved by integrating a gender perspective through the entire R&I cycle 'from the setting of research priorities through defining concepts, formulating research questions, developing methodologies, gathering and analyzing sex/gender disaggregated data, to evaluating and reporting results and transferring them to markets into products and innovations which will benefit all citizens and promote gender equality' (Horizon Europe Programme Guide 2023). This chimes well with a gender mainstreaming approach in research which aims to ensure that gender issues are considered when defining the research agenda, the scope and purpose of the project, as well as identifying appropriate methodologies and dissemination and evaluation strategies (United Nations 2002, p. 17).

REDEMOS' **research priorities and agenda** revolve around the idea that the EU needs to demonstrate sensitivity towards the concerns, needs and agency of EU eastern neighbourhood citizens at the non-state level. Robust commitment via enhanced strategies, diplomacy and funding with governments at the state level, ensuring that democracy practices, and the construction of a workable demos, is placed more consistently and coherently at the center of its approach. The need for more effective, impactful, resilient and sustainable EU democracy support in the eastern neighbourhood and more robust democratic systems in each of the six neighbours is in the interest of both men and women in these countries.

The EU democracy collaboration framework that REDEMOS seeks to develop, explore and employ is based on the premise that, among other factors, processes of democratic change, and the quality of

democracy, are significantly strengthened and more resilient if they can also be driven by and be embedded in the active participation of underrepresented groups such as women. REDEMOS links up with research that shows that gender equality on the one hand and democratisation and democracy on the other form mutually reinforcing relationships and that gender equality is part and parcel of a strong and sustained demos. It is embedded in the emergent body of scholarship that aims at cross-fertilising (EU) foreign policy analysis with gender and international feminist theory. Consequently, research activities conducted in WP2-6 contain a strong gender component in so far as they scrutinise, inter alia, the extent to which (a) past EU democracy support efforts, (b) actions of democracy-averse domestic and international norm contenders, and (c) the domestic opportunity-structure in the eastern neighbourhood marginalised or empowered women as actors of change. This strong gender focus is further advanced by the fact that WP7, focusing on images of the EU as a democracy supporter and how these shaped EU approaches, examines discourses, narratives and perceptions also in a gender-sensitive manner, allowing for greater analytical differentiation. The strict pursuit of the latter throughout the project and the transversality of gender enables REDEMOS to ensure that its final policy recommendations and the policy toolkit for supporting democracy collaboration that it will propose are fully gender mainstreamed.

In **conceptualising the central notion of demos**, the project does not assume that ‘citizens’ as such represent a uniform, undifferentiated group. On the contrary, REDEMOS is interested in understanding the role of marginalised and underrepresented groups, such as women, sexual and ethnic minorities and rural communities in democratisation processes and international democracy support. This represents a cross-cutting issue but is addressed particularly in WP4 through a critical analysis of the role of four main social, economic, cultural and statehood-related factors in fostering/inhibiting democracy building.

The project **methodology** aims to ensure that the differentiated views and concerns of both women and men are both considered by using sex-disaggregated data to the extent possible. The **interviews** with stakeholders within governance structures and civil society actors; the **Q-Methodology** to assess stakeholders’ priorities and preferences; the **mini-publics** in the form of assemblies with local stakeholders and policymakers; the **survey** of key grassroots democracy actors; and the **focus groups** and **online debates** with EU citizens, will all seek the inputs of women as well as men, in order to gain a more nuanced understanding of: the interaction between different policy stakeholders; state-society relations; interactivity with the EU and the international community; inter- and intra-institutional and societal relations; the support and demand for particular types of EU actions, policies, implementation mechanisms, and policy goals. The REDEMOS research methods are gender mainstreamed to the extent that they target both men and women as research participants, but also in so far as the content of the questions, questionnaires and issues discussed is concerned, including inter alia topics such as the role of women in democratisation processes, gender equality and the existence of equal opportunities for men and women in eastern neighbourhood societies.

- **RECOMMENDATION:** REDEMOS should continue to encourage and foster the integration of a gender dimension in its research content, including in defining concepts, developing methodologies, gathering and analysing sex/gender disaggregated data.
- **SUPPORTING MEASURE(S):**

- Work package leaders and contributors will be encouraged to meet at least once with Gender Board members in order to discuss concrete ideas for integrating gender into research content.
- REDEMOS will offer additional training on gender mainstreaming in research.
- REDEMOS researchers will be instructed to pay particular attention to gender balance in reference lists and bibliographies and adopt gender neutral language.

3.3. Gender-sensitive communication, dissemination and impact

The gender mainstreaming measures outlined above aim to produce gender-sensitive project results, by proposing policy solutions (i.e. the REDEMOS Policy Toolkit) which support an equitable distribution of benefits and opportunities between men and women and empower women and their role in democratic governance and public life. The project's impact is thus likely to be enhanced because gender-sensitive research reaches broader target groups. Findings and recommendations on narrowing gender gaps and strengthening gender equality will be prominently disseminated and included in policy discussions.

Gender-sensitive communication and dissemination require reflective and considerate use of language, imagery and symbols, to ensure that women's views and experiences are not only taken into account, but also accurately and meaningfully depicted. In order to achieve this, there are several key guidelines that should be observed in the context of communication and dissemination activities.³

➤ **RECOMMENDATIONS:**

Communication

- Masculine pronouns should not be used to represent both women and men
- Terms that diminish women—like “lady” or “girl” should be avoided
- Reference should not be made to women's [or men's] appearance or marital status
- Avoid traditional concepts such as “head of the household” which limit representation
- Use gender inclusive job titles
- Be proactively gender inclusive. Include images of women in active roles as researchers, etc.
- Aim for gender balance when portraying domestic situations
- Do not use sexualised, or sexually explicit imagery

Dissemination

- Be mindful of gender differences in social media use and content sharing and aim to target and engage both men and women
- Prior to disseminating any information the text should be gender-proofed to ensure that high standards are applied to the dissemination of content
- Ensure that dissemination activities are not ‘target blind’, but rather reach out to both men and women, as well as other relevant groups for REDEMOS (minorities, rural communities)

³<https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/documents/downloadPublic?documentIds=080166e5a02ab81f&appId=PPGMS>

- Gender perspectives should be highlighted in research content, but also in reports and publications targeting decision makers and the public, as well as on the REDEMOS website and social media accounts.
- **SUPPORTING MEASURE(S):**
 - REDEMOS will consult with civil society organisations, scholars and other stakeholders working on gender issues about best practices for gender-sensitive and inclusive communication and dissemination
 - Based on the above, REDEMOS will produce guidelines for gender-sensitive and inclusive communication and dissemination to be shared with all partners
 - All partners will be encouraged to monitor REDEMOS communication and dissemination activities, and report issues of concern to the Gender Board

3.4 Implementation, monitoring and evaluation

While gender mainstreaming as a strategy to achieve gender equality is fairly straightforward on a general level, identifying specific measures to implement it under distinct project-specific circumstances can be challenging. Following on from the recommendations and supporting measures identified in the previous sections of this Gender Mainstreaming Plan, REDEMOS is committed to supporting its researchers in acquiring greater understanding of the mainstreaming approach and developing concrete ways to implement it in research content and methodologies. At the same time, it is important that the project itself, in the composition of its research teams, as well as in its communication and dissemination activities, implements gender-sensitive approaches.

Gender analysis designed to identify gender needs, challenges and opportunities in research is a key starting point for gender mainstreaming and will be conducted across the three previous project phases through, inter alia, cooperation between the Gender Board and Work Package leaders, as well as consultations with stakeholders from academia and the civil society with relevant gender expertise. Gender equality training and capacity building initiatives will be implemented to improve gender equality competencies. Project staff, partners and stakeholders will be trained on a variety of topics including gender awareness, collection and analysis of gender sensitive data and gender sensitive decision making. Collaboration with gender equality experts or organisations will focus on drawing on their experience and promoting capacity building.

Communication and outreach will be based on a gender-responsive approach. Gender balanced representation will be ensured at public events, conferences and publications. The results and conclusions of the project will be disseminated among the target audience and stakeholders in a gender-sensitive manner, which will increase awareness and impact.

Engagement with relevant stakeholders will be a priority. Collaboration with gender equality advocates, organisations and networks will be encouraged to draw on their expertise and promote synergy. Feedback and suggestions from gender equality stakeholders will be sought through participatory processes.

By adhering to this comprehensive implementation, monitoring and evaluation strategy, REDEMOS will actively promote gender mainstreaming and promote gender equality.

- **RECOMMENDATION:** REDEMOS should ensure that the implementation of gender mainstreaming efforts is being regularly monitored and evaluated.
- **SUPPORTING MEASURE(S):** the Gender Board will monitor and evaluate gender mainstreaming approaches and activities within individual work packages in order to foster commitment to gender equality and the gender mainstreaming strategy among partners.

Table 1: Gender mainstreaming in research: recommendations and supporting measures

	Recommendations	Supporting measures
Equal opportunities for women and men in research	Partners should continue to strive towards gender balanced research teams as they recruit new team members, and make sure to avoid gender bias and discrimination in selection and recruitment procedures, working conditions and culture and management practices.	REDEMOS will offer training on gender sensitivity in recruitment and management practices.
Gender expertise of researchers	REDEMOS should ensure that the perspectives of researchers with gender expertise are appropriately considered and widely shared across work packages.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Relevant experts will be invited to occasionally give relevant talks to partners and provide advice on how gender angles can be incorporated into project research. • Relevant resources will be made available to partners in the relevant shared Teams channels.
Integrating gender into research content	REDEMOS should continue to encourage and foster the integration of a gender dimension in its research content, incl. in defining concepts, developing methodologies, gathering and analysing sex/gender disaggregated data.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • WP leaders and contributors will be encouraged to meet at least once with Gender Board members to discuss concrete ideas for integrating gender into research content. • REDEMOS will offer additional training on gender mainstreaming in research. • REDEMOS researchers will be instructed to pay particular attention to gender balance in reference lists and bibliographies and adopt gender neutral language.
Gender-sensitive communications, dissemination and impact	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Masculine pronouns should not be used to represent both women and men • Terms that diminish women—like “lady” or “girl” should be avoided • Reference should not be made to women’s [or men’s] appearance or marital status • Avoid traditional concepts such as “head of the household” which limit representation • Use gender inclusive job titles 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • REDEMOS will consult with civil society organisations, scholars and other stakeholders working on gender issues about best practices for gender-sensitive and inclusive communication and dissemination. • REDEMOS will produce guidelines for gender-sensitive and inclusive communication and dissemination to be shared with all partners

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Be proactively gender inclusive. Include images of women in active roles as researchers, etc. • Aim for gender balance when portraying domestic situations • Do not use sexualised, or sexually explicit imagery • Be mindful of gender differences in social media use and content sharing and aim to target and engage both men and women • Prior to disseminating any information the text should be gender-proofed to ensure that high standards are applied to the dissemination of content • Ensure that dissemination activities are not 'target blind', but rather reach out to both men and women, as well as other relevant groups for REDEMOS (minorities, rural communities) • Gender perspectives should be highlighted in research content, but also in reports and publications targeting decision makers and the public, as well as on the REDEMOS website and social media accounts. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All partners will be encouraged to monitor REDEMOS communication and dissemination activities, and report issues of concern to the Gender Board.
<p>Implementation, monitoring and evaluation</p>	<p>REDEMOS should ensure that the implementation of gender mainstreaming efforts is being regularly monitored and evaluated.</p>	<p>The Gender Board will monitor and evaluate gender mainstreaming approaches and activities within individual work packages in order to foster commitment to gender equality and the gender mainstreaming strategy among partners.</p>

REFERENCES

Communication from the Commission to the European Parliament, the Council, the European Economic and Social Committee and the Committee of the Regions (2020) A Union of Equality: Gender Equality Strategy 2020-2025, available at: <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=CELEX%3A52020DC0152>.

Council of the European Union (2018) Council Conclusions on Women, Peace and Security, 10 December 2018, available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/37412/st15086-en18.pdf>.

European Commission (1999) Women and Science. Mobilising women to enrich European research. Communication from the Commission. COM (99) 76 final, 17 February 1999, available at: <http://aei.pitt.edu/13321/>.

European Commission (2009) Toolkit Gender in EU-funded research, available at: <https://op.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/c17a4eba-49ab-40f1-bb7b-bb6faaf8dec8>.

European Commission (2023) Horizon Europe Programme Guide, available at: https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/docs/2021-2027/horizon/guidance/programme-guide_horizon_en.pdf.

European Commission and the High Representative of the Union for Foreign Affairs and Security Policy (2020) EU Gender Action Plan on Gender Equality and Women's Empowerment in External Action 2021–2025 (GAP III), available at: https://ec.europa.eu/commission/presscorner/detail/en/IP_20_2184.

European External Action Service (2018) EU Strategic Approach to Women, Peace and Security, available at: <https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/37412/st15086-en18.pdf>.

European Parliament (2020) Report on Gender Equality in EU's foreign and security policy, available at: https://www.europarl.europa.eu/doceo/document/A-9-2020-0145_EN.html.

European Union (2012) Consolidated version of the Treaty on the Functioning of the European Union, available at: <https://www.refworld.org/docid/52303e8d4.html>.

Mihajlović Trbovc, Jovana and Ana Hofman () Toolkit for Integrating Gender Sensitive Approach into Research and Teaching, GARCIA Working Papers 6, available at: https://eige.europa.eu/sites/default/files/garcia_toolkit_gender_research_teaching.pdf

The New European Consensus on Development 'Our world, our dignity, our future' (2017), available at: https://www.consilium.europa.eu/media/24004/european-consensus-on-development-2-june-2017-clean_final.pdf.

UN Women (2022). Handbook on Gender Mainstreaming for Gender Equality Results, available at: https://reliefweb.int/report/world/handbook-gender-mainstreaming-gender-equality-results?gclid=EAlalQobChMI_LOz69uh_wIVEWAYCh3K-gUgEAAYBCAAEgJ0NvD_BwE

United Nations (2002) Gender Mainstreaming. An Overview.